

Unpleasant emotions: Designing for stress

The need for guidelines when developing products or systems for use in stressful situations

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Abstract

This article points out the need for guidelines in the development processes of products and systems intended for use under stress. Typical products are safety equipment and military equipment. Whereas traditional human factors research is mostly concerned with removing or reducing the actual cause of stress from a work environment, the approach of this article looks at the stress responses in the user, and how the designer should relate to these when designing products or systems for use in stressful situations. The result of the article is a proposed set of guidelines that could be employed by designers who carry the intention of making better solutions with respect to stress.

Keywords: Stress, interface design, product design, human factors, emergency equipment, safety, military, stressors, cognitive performance, guidelines, unpleasant emotions

1. Introduction

The human performance, both physical and psychological, in a given situation will depend on a large number of factors. This article is based on literature and research related to human factors and the psychological phenomenon, stress. The referred examples show that the physiological changes that occur in the human body during stress will influence the physical and psychological capabilities in a person, and often in a negative way. Hence, one of the aims of applying ergonomics to a workstation will be to avoid stress. In traditional human factors methodology there exist numerous guidelines for how to prevent stress situations in a work environment. This is done by removing or reducing the actual source of stress, the so-called stressor; examples are Sanders & McCormick (1992), Grandjean (1980) and Vavik & Øritsland (1999).

But what if the traumatic situation, e.g. a fire, cannot be avoided? How should an interface be designed to assure maximum functionality in such a situation? Can the product properties contribute to reduce stress when the stressors are significant? How should designers think and act when developing a product that is likely to be used by a frightened person who tries to utilize the product in order to save his life? During the preface of this article I found no specific tool intended exclusively for this topic.

The aim of this article is therefore to justify the need for, and suggest, some general guidelines to employ in interface design, based on the stress affected bodily responses and relevant product design examples. These guidelines are intended to create a platform for developing products in a context where the user will be operating in an unbalanced psychological state; stress. The figure below shows a model of the article's focus compared to traditional human factors.

Figure 1 : the article's approach to stress

2. Stress

Everybody has felt it, either suddenly or built up over time. We are all familiar with the term. Stress is usually an unpleasant feeling that you would like to go away. For example, you can feel stressed at work trying to finish a job before deadline. But this kind of stress will differ from the stress related to more traumatic experiences such as a car accident or a war related situation, and the extent of bodily responses will be greater in the latter two examples. Still the situations have a lot in common: they both deal with stress. So, how can we define stress?

2.1 Definition of stress

In this article a functional definition of stress will be used:

When a body in homeostatic balance (i.e. temperature, glucose level etc. are as close to ideal as possible) is exposed to a stressor (anything in the environment that knocks the body out of homeostasis), the body will try to adjust itself to the new conditions, and the stress response is the array of physiological adaptations that ultimately re-establishes balance. (Sapolsky, 2003)

Some researchers emphasize that stress is a multidimensional concept that includes the stress stimuli (stressor), the processing system including cognitive assessment of the stimuli, and the stress responses. (Rosenzweig, Leiman & Breedlove, 1996) These kinds of thoughts are found in the physiological stress theory launched by the acclaimed psychologist Hans Selye in the 1950's. He named his theory the General Adaptation Syndrome and it explains how the body reacts in three different stages when encountering stress stimuli. (Beredskapsstyrelsen, 1995)

1. Alarm state (awareness of the danger, shock)
 - Activation of the sympathetic nervous system
2. Resistance state (panic, anxiety, seeking to solve the problem, coping with it)
 - Release of stress hormones
3. Exhaustion state (the problem cannot be solved, surrender, apathy, depression)
 - Collapse

In contemporary studies this concept of stress and disease has been modified; some investigators note that the common ingredient to stressful stimuli is uncertainty or unpredictability about how to gain positive control (Levine and Ursin, 1980, in Rosenzweig, Leiman & Breedlove, 1996).

2.2 How does stress arise?

The psychological phenomenon stress will always be provoked by extreme changes in our environments, so-called stressors. These stressors can be categorized in three different groups: psychological, physical and social (Beredskapsstyrelsen 1995). Here are some examples:

Physical:

- Cold, heat
- Physical strain/muscular overload
- Noise (Sudden loud noise over 100dB will immediately trigger stress-functions)
- Motion
- Lighting
- Vibrations
- Ventilation
- Hunger
- Malnutrition
- Fatigue
- Insufficient hygiene
- Altitude sickness
- Illness/ disease

Psychological:

- Lack of stimulus
- Monotonous work
- Loneliness
- Little variation in daily life
- Excessive stimulus
- Unsolved problems
- Heavy Workload
- Time pressure
- Fear and anxiety
- Uncertainty

Sociological: Bad housing conditions
Lack of belonging
Unemployment
Poverty
Threatened social status

2.3 Bodily responses to stress

When exposed to a stressor, we will experience this in numerous ways. Some will feel dizzy, some may break out in cold sweats, and a few might even develop ulcers. The whole bodily response system is similar in all mammals, thus a frightened zebra trying to escape the jaws of a hungry predator would have undergone more or less the same physiological process as a person trying to escape from a fire.

Wickens, Lee, Liu and Becker (2004) divide these stress effects into four different groups:

1. The psychological experience. Often, but not always, we will be able to report an unpleasant feeling as a consequence of the stressor.

2. Physiological changes. These are mainly physiological defence mechanisms that occur in order to prepare for fight or flight, and to retrieve the homeostasis balance:

- secretion of hormones from the adrenal glands (epinephrine, norepinephrine, cortisol)
- expansion of the respiratory passage and blood vessels
- increased blood pressure and heart frequency
- expansion of pupils
- release of sugar from the liver to the muscles
- closure of urethra and anus
- rise in body heat
- release of body sweat to avoid overheating
- tension of muscles
- short-winded, asthma (THELMA, 2002)
- lack of appetite (Bjorkli, Stene, Jenssen, 2003)

3. Psychological interference. Stressors affect the efficiency of information processing, generally by degrading performance

4. Long-term negative effects on health, such as reduced immune system and ulcers.

The exact stress responses of an individual will be difficult to predict, as they will vary according to the individual's ability to cope (Eid & Johnsen, 2005). The kind of effects, and the strength of them, will depend on the situation and the individual, but the stress responses are all a part of the same psychobiological process. Any stressor will immediately activate the sympathetic part of the autonomic nervous system, and the adrenal glands will start the secretion of two types of hormones: epinephrine, also known as adrenalin, and glucocorticoid (cortisol in humans). In mammals, like antelopes, this process is often triggered by an acute physical challenge, such as fleeing from a lion.

Epinephrine and cortisol mobilize energy for muscles, increase the cardiovascular tone so oxygen can travel more quickly along the blood stream, and reduces other unnecessary functions, like growth. "The hormones work at different speeds. In a fight-or-flee scenario, epinephrine is the

one handing out the guns; glucocorticoids are the ones drawing up blueprints for new aircraft carriers needed for the war effort.” (Sapolsky, 2003) Thus, the epinephrine reacts much quicker, more or less kick-starting your body within milliseconds, while cortisol needs some 15 minutes before the concentration in the blood reaches a maximum (Hubbard, Kalimi, Witorsch, 1986, cited by Tuvnes 2005).

3. Responses that affects interaction

In addition to the mentioned responses in the 4-way division by Wickens, Lee, Liu and Becker, other scientists have made supplementary discoveries, sometimes related to very specific research areas or product groups such as aviation, or working environments with extreme temperatures. This chapter summarises the relevant findings with regards to interaction, and points out the essential responses that should be evaluated during the task of developing guidelines for an interaction designer.

The figure underneath shows that a stressor may produce direct or indirect effects. Direct stress responses will influence the quality of information received by the receptors, or the precision of the response, whereas the indirect responses will affect the efficiency of information processing. This should encourage the designer to take certain precautions when developing the interface of a system or a product.

Figure 1: How stressors affect interaction (Freely adapted from Wickens, Lee, Liu & Becker 2005)

3.1 Cognition

A lot of stressors will have an indirect effect on the body, i.e. impact on information processing. A person exposed to a stressor will often experience a rise in psychological arousal. This is a consequence of the body preparing to fight or flee. Indicators such as heart rate, expansion of pupils etc can measure the level of arousal. Yerkes & Dodson stated with their law of 1908 that cognitive performance increases with the level of arousal up to a certain point, the Optimum Level of Arousal (OLA), before the performance suddenly drops if the individual becomes over aroused. If the task is considered complex, the OLA will be reached sooner than if the task were simple. Also, experiments have proved that beyond the OLA, the creative ability in problem solving will be reduced. This is known as cognitive tunnelling and describes the tendency to focus exclusively on one hypothesis of what is going on, and ignore a potentially more creative diagnosis by considering a wider range of options.

It should also be noted that in some cases heat and cold stress would slow down the cognitive process. This effect would require the system to wait longer for the human input.

3.2 Speech

Certain stressors can give rise to stress responses that affect our voice. Doherty (1991) has demonstrated that there are identifiable changes in voice pattern as a function of task-induced stress. These changes are actually so evident, that researchers try to develop tools for measuring the actual level of stress by analyzing voice patterns. For example, Jones (1990), (in Doherty, 1991), found that, for extreme stress situations, both the increase in speaking fundamental frequency and the decrease in vocal jitter were statistically significant.

3.3 Hearing

The sense of hearing is very sensitive and useful in a lot of operational situations. But the sensitivity will also attend to stressors, both directly and indirectly. Memory tests have proved

that background noise is very restraining to short term memory performance (direct impact) and learning (indirect) (Eid & Johnsen, 2005).

Hugdahl showed in 1995 that the brain does not automatically process auditory information from the left and the right ear in the same manner. Further studies have shown that some people have a tendency to perceive auditory stimulus in right ear better than equal stimulus in left ear. This kind of difference in auditory processing of stimulus between right and left cerebral hemisphere accentuates with stress and fatigue (Johnsen, Laberg, Eid & Hugdahl, 2003). Eid and Johnsen (2005) state the importance of these stress effects: “In operational situations this could be of critical relevance, and design of equipment should therefore aim at reducing possible errors caused by stress.”

3.4 Vision

Known functional vision problems caused by or associated with near point vision stress include: accommodative disorders (insufficiency, ill-sustained, infacility); abnormal heterophorias (esophoria, high exophoria); and vergence disorders. These vision disorders cause problems with acuity, comfort, and performance (Gruning 1985). We also know that the pupils expand under stress, even though it's uncertain how much effect this has with respect to increased light sensitivity or field of vision (interview, Tuvnes 2005).

As mentioned under cognition, a stressed person will sometimes put all his attention to one task or object, often the stressor itself. This experience called tunnelling, will sometimes also affect the eyesight. Visual tunnelling could be treated separately as this topic seems to be left out in many books on human factors, although the work of Diffrient, Tilley and Bardagjy of 1974 states an “emergency field of view” of 30° compared the normal 60°. However, the findings of Rogers (2003) suggest that this effect is actually much greater. Rogers examined the influence of life-event stress on visual peripheral narrowing in a real-life stress situation. The state of anxiety and peripheral vision were measured in competing athletes. The stress condition was obtained by assessing the athletes within 2 hours of a competition. The real-life stress condition had a larger effect on state anxiety and peripheral narrowing than the laboratory-induced situations used in previous research, with effect sizes twice and three times as large as those reported in the

literature. All athletes experienced significant reductions in peripheral vision prior to competition, regardless of life-event stress or hardiness levels.

3.5 Motory precision

When exposed to a stressor, the body will immediately enter a state of alertness, preparing to fight or flee. There is a rapid release of sugar from the liver to the muscles that enable you for more enduring physical tasks. But if you don't use this extra energy, the result is muscle tension. Some people will shiver and quiver as a stress reaction; some will even tremble with anger, hence the expression. Muscle tension has a negative impact on fine motory precision, and limits the accuracy in certain operations. This effect itself can be a potential stressor in some situations, as the user might get frustrated and annoyed due to his or her inability to perform the desired actions.

Cold as a stressor will also influence the coordinated motor performance, and the parts of the body first affected would usually be fingers, hands and feet. Cold stress will slow down the response time of the nerves by about $1.7 \text{ ms}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Handbook for Work in Cold, THELMA 2002)

Another stressor that gives direct effect on the precision of the response mechanisms is the impact of vibrations, such as those omitted from an electric drill or the rattling in a small airplane. Vibrations mainly affect your motory precision, but also your vision at high exposures.

3.6 Other stress responses

A few other responses should also be considered, even though not so directly linked to interaction. One issue is that some people will sweat excessively when stressed, particularly in their hands. This kind of stress response is meant to compensate for the rise in body heat and will avoid overheating. It should also be mentioned that the stress response of short-windedness and asthma, as well as contractions in the upper part of the respiratory system when exposed to cold stress, could influence a person's ability to perform physically enduring tasks.

4. Control

As mentioned earlier, contemporary psychological studies emphasize how stressors relate to uncertainty or unpredictability about how to gain positive control. Having control of a situation will often imply that the body is in balance, and losing control will knock the body out of homeostasis. However, the notion of not having control is difficult to categorise as a specific stress response, but nonetheless this subchapter tries to emphasize the relevance of this feeling.

The most commonly studied real-life stress situation is military training, especially aviator training and parachute training, where stress involves fear of bodily harm and fear of failure (Rosenzweig, Leiman, Breedlove, 1996).

Studies of Norwegian military recruits showed that successful parachute-jumps quickly led to a decrease in the pituitary-adrenal response, which can be explained by a theory that the feeling of control and positive expectations to the outcome of the situation reduces stress.

This study is coherent with the findings of Rob Sapolsky who points out that a baboon will secrete fewer stress hormones in fighting situations with rivaling baboon males if he wins and experiences a rise in the baboon community ranking; he feels that life is improving, he has a sense of control.

A new article by Amat, Baratta, Paul, Bland ET. Al. released in March 2005 is based on an experiment where rats were placed in cages and given electrical shocks in their tails. Some of the rats had the option of spinning a wheel, and the spinning would make the test personnel stop the electrical shocks stop for a while. These rats proved considerable lower levels of stress hormones in their blood samples than the rats that were not given the option of controlling their situation. These results led the scientists to the findings that there is a particular area of the brain that analyses the threat and determines if the danger has passed.

5. Designing for stress

Biologists and psychologists have made extensive research on stressors and stress effects, but what about designers? How do they relate to the topic? This chapter refers to an interview with the managing director of the Norwegian product design company THELMA that has been involved in several projects involving safety in marine environments.

Products such as life vests and survival suits are essential at sea and in many cases made mandatory by the government. But unfortunately, even though there is a general acknowledgment of this kind of equipment, there exists some terrible examples of safety products that fail their mission, and becomes a potential hazard instead. The tragic accident of the express marine vessel Sleipner in the winter of 1999 was a devastating example of design failures, where the report (partly conducted by THELMA) states that poorly designed and dysfunctional life vests caused several casualties. One can argue that the issue of stress has not been handled correctly from the manufacturer's side when the life vests have laces as its securing mechanism.

THELMA is currently working on improving a feature on a survival suit for helicopters. All personnel being transported to offshore rigs on Norwegian continental shelf wear this waterproof suit. In case of an emergency landing, the suit needs to be waterproof due to the likelihood of evacuating in cold water. The need for rapid evacuation is crucial as the helicopter will fill with water and sink. Estimated time for successful evacuation is 30-40 seconds, but people exposed to cold stressors get short-winded and manage only to hold their breath for 15-20 seconds. This problem gave rise to the idea of letting the user breathe in a closed system during the evacuation and avoid inhalation of water and eventual drowning. This extra lung is what THELMA is currently improving as the old solution proved to be too complicated to use in a stressed situation. Their methods are mostly concerned about making things easier and more intuitive in use. "It needs to be fool proof as some stressed people tend to forget safety procedures they learned at a safety course a few years ago" (interview, Påsche, 2005). Hence the development team added a water-dissolvable spring releasing mechanism that will close the breathing system immediately after contact with water, just in case the stressed person fails to do so himself. Påsche says that if the stress effect involved in a certain job or task cannot be avoided, then the whole task has to be redesigned. I.e. if the cold exposure on the fingers is unbearable when performing an operation

outdoors, don't put on thicker gloves; make the task simpler, and reduce the time of exposure instead!

(Other industry examples have been withdrawn to shorten the article)

6. Suggested guidelines

The table below is a suggestion to guidelines that could be employed by any designer who is working with products in a stress context. The designer should evaluate which stress responses that are likely to occur in every specific case, and which of the corresponding actions are necessary to take. The contents of the table are merely meant as advice and not as absolute answers to the problems, and a thorough understanding of the design process is essential.

Table 1: Suggested Guidelines

Stressor type	Stress response	Designers action
Direct interference	Disturbed vision	Check for sufficient lighting, use of colours, contrast, font size, easily read symbols etc.
	Visual tunnelling	Concentrate the area in need of visual focus
	Voice jitter	Test thoroughly for sensitivity weaknesses in all voice-based interfaces
	Reduced hearing	Avoid nuances in stereo audio as data input
	Shivers	Avoid high demand of physical accuracy
	Reduced sensitivity	Avoid extended use of tactile feedback
	Slow reactions	Avoid interfaces which requires quick response by the user
	Sweaty hands	Make handles and contact surfaces in non-slippery materials
	Reduced breathing capability	Avoid physically demanding tasks
Indirect interference	Sense of lack of control	Give the user frequent, readily available feedback In all possible ways, give the user a notion of control
	Reduced short-term memory	Keep things as simple and intuitive as possible. Use existing conventions Keep knowledge in the world
	Reduced long-term memory	Simplify every task
	Cognitive tunnelling	Reduce number of inputs Concentrate the elements in need of attention Give precise instructions of what to do, not instructions of what NOT to do Give instructions in chronological order

7. Discussion

As mentioned in the previous chapters, traditional human factors methodology tends to focus solely on stressors rather than the bodily stress responses. In addition, most of the research done on stress has been done in affiliation with area-specific studies, either very focused on a single system or product (e.g. fighter cockpits), or concerned with a specific medical or psychological phenomenon (e.g. hormone-research). As a consequence, the information-gathering process of this article has been slightly difficult. First of all, it is almost certain that the proposed guidelines are missing out on some important issues that deserve to be included. Interesting results from various area-specific researches may have failed to be located during literature search and interviews. One of the reasons for this is obviously the practice of keeping experiment data confidential, especially within military research, and commercial research. Further there's an issue regarding the problem of stress research itself. On one hand you have the practical problems regarding experiments and data gathering: Can you provoke a real-life stress situation in a laboratory? Is it ethically sound to do research in live-stress situations, e.g. monitoring policemen and soldiers in action? On the other hand, Hammonds, the author of *Judgments under stress* (2000), argues that the real problem in stress research is the lack of a coherent body of knowledge, a framework or principle upon which all the stress related research can rest. Hence all the research that has been done in the last 20 years fails to compare on an identical level. This complicates things, both practically, and from a scientific-philosophical point of view, when trying to draw general conclusions from the different findings.

The latter seems to be the central issue in this article. The selection of stress responses that have been presented in theory, and later employed in the guidelines, is chosen from a number of different sources regardless of the validity of the sources' applied research methods. The selection itself is based upon the judgement of the author, and does not rest upon a common academic consensus of stress responses crucial to interaction. However, they have been carefully selected due to their apparent relevance for interaction. The subdivision of the stress responses into two groups was considered the most appropriate one by the author, but other possibilities include a ranking of importance. The true aim of this article is to make a useful tool for designers, and though some might find the guidelines as a somewhat crude overview of common issues

related to stress, they will hopefully yield a good starting point to any design project that will deal with the topic.

8. Conclusion

This article has pointed out the need for guidelines in development processes of products and systems intended for a stressed user-situation. It also states the lack of such guidelines in traditional human factors methodology. The result of the article is a proposed set of guidelines that could be employed by designers who carries the intention of making better solutions with respect to stress. However, the guidelines and the topic in general should be questioned and taken further in every respect, with the aim of developing a broader, stronger interdisciplinary framework for stress research.

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